

2022-2023 Fellowship Class

Fellowship Program Area Executive Branch

Applicant Dr. Jessica Burnett Skills Data Visualization/Infographics,
Forecasting, Land/Biodiversity
Management, Software Development,
Statistical Analysis

Affiliation U.S. Geological Survey

Title Mendenhall Postdoctoral Fellow and Research Ecologist

Primary Email jburnett@usgs.gov

Email Type Work

Alternate Email jessicaleighburnett@Gmail.com

Email Type Work

Cell Phone [REDACTED]

Home Phone [REDACTED]

Country USA

Street [REDACTED]

City [REDACTED]

State/Province [REDACTED]

Zip [REDACTED]

Gender [REDACTED]

Ethnicity No

Race White

Disability Decline to identify

Protected Veteran I am not a protected veteran

Initial Eligibility Self-Check

Are you a US Citizen (or dual citizen of the United States and another country)? Yes

Are you a current federal employee (includes Title 42 positions and Presidential Management Fellowships)? No

Are you a current American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS) employee or are you currently conducting paid work for AAAS? No

Will you have completed a qualifying degree by the application deadline? Yes

Are you in compliance with U.S. Selective Service registration requirements? Yes

Applicant Background

Qualifying Degree Institution University of Nebraska-Lincoln

Qualifying Degree Type	PhD	Qualifying Degree Discipline Category	Biological/Agricultural /Environmental Life Sciences
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Qualifying Degree Year Conferred	2019	Qualifying Degree Discipline Specific	Environmental Life Sciences
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Qualifying Degree Field of Study	Applied Ecology
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Dissertation Title (if applicable)	Regime Shift Detection Methods for the Practical Ecologist
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Upload CV

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Citizenship	U.S Only
STPF Affiliation	New Applicant
Current Employment Sector	Government (local, state, federal, international)
AAAS Membership	I am not currently a AAAS member, but I will enroll as a member if selected to receive a fellowship.
Each fall, the AAAS S&T Policy Fellowships connect applicants with fellows to offer support and resources about the application. Would you like to participate in this program and be contacted by a current or alumni fellow?	Yes, I would like to be contacted by a fellow and give STPF permission to share my contact information with the fellow.
When did you first learn about the AAAS S&T Policy Fellowships?	1-3 years ago
How did you first learn about the AAAS S&T Policy Fellowships?	Current/Alumni STPF Fellow
Please Specify:	A colleague, Judit Ungavari, posted something about STPF on their LinkedIn.
Where did you hear about the AAAS S&T Policy Fellowships?	Other
Please Specify:	LinkedIn via previous Alumni's post
Which of the AAAS S&T Policy Fellowships sources were of most value when considering the program?	Other
Please Specify:	Pers. comms. with multiple previous alumni, including and beyond my immediate network.

References

Reference #1

First Name	R. Sky
Last Name	Bristol
Organization	U.S. Geological Survey
Title	Supervisory Biologist, Biogeographic Characterization
Email	[REDACTED]
Phone Number	[REDACTED]
How long have you known this reference?	1 to 5 years
In what capacity do you know this reference?	Current supervisor and mentor.

References

Reference #2

First Name	Karen
Last Name	Jenni
Organization	U.S. Geological Survey
Title	Decision Scientist
Email	[REDACTED]
Phone Number	[REDACTED]
How long have you known this reference?	1 to 5 years
In what capacity do you know this reference?	Professional mentor

References

Reference #3

First Name	Brian
Last Name	Wee
Organization	Massive Connections, LLC
Title	Founder and Managing Director
Email	[REDACTED]
Phone Number	[REDACTED]
How long have you known this reference?	1 to 5 years

In what capacity do you know this reference?

Colleague and Co-PI on Earth Science Information Partnership (ESIP) lab project.

Applicant Interests, Skills, & Statements

Policy Interests First Preference	Environment and Climate Science
Policy Interests Second Preference	Forestry, Water, and Natural Resources
Policy Interests Third Preference	Oversight and Government Reform
Skills and Proficiencies	Data Visualization/Infographics Forecasting Land/Biodiversity Management Software Development Statistical Analysis

Professional Bio (1500 Character Limit)

As a first generation college student with major psychiatric disorders, I am extraordinarily proud of my career and contributions to science to date. After completing community college, I studied Wildlife Ecology and Conservation at the University of Florida with the intent of pursuing a career in veterinary medicine. Upon exposure to research and academia, however, I was fortunate to have the opportunity to pursue a Master's degree at my alma mater. My graduate training provided me with a strong foundation in applied statistics with application to empirical Earth observations data. My Master's graduate research program focused largely on urban ecology, exploring the relationship of urbanization and non-native avifauna. I received a Ph.D. in Natural Resources Science and Applied Ecology from the University of Nebraska-Lincoln where I, uniquely, leveraged only extant and simulated data to advance the methods for detecting rapid change and regime shifts in ecological systems. My research as a Mendenhall Postdoctoral Fellow with the U.S. Geological Survey focused on improving usefulness and usability of data, information, and other actionable intelligence for stakeholders.

I have a deep interest in continuing to work to improve the connectivity among science producers and science users, and wish to bridge the science-implementation gap in natural resources management and conservation using the concepts and technologies associated with Knowledge Management.

Applicant Statement (7000 Character Limit)

The value of publicly-funded science can be improved through increasing the accessibility, interoperability, and transparency of data, information, and decision-making processes. As an applied ecologist with a persistent passion in informatics, I believe I can successfully leverage a AAAS Science and Technology Policy Fellowship to work towards this goal. While my quantitative aptitude and disciplinary expertise could be leveraged to meet specific science needs, I would very much be interested in learning about and contributing to my host agency's program planning, particularly with respect to how it connects and leverages its science and human capital capacities. I am keen to continue a career as a civil servant as I feel there is great responsibility and an additional sense of pride that comes with being a federal scientist. The application and advancement of statistical and numerical methods for gaining meaningful inference from ecological data was an important part of my education, research, and professional development. Whereas my formal training and predoctoral research focused largely on advancing methods for collecting

and analyzing observational data. As a civil servant and postdoctoral researcher, I have expanded my interests to focus on improving the ways in which inferences from ecological data are found and applied. My most recent work includes designing and creating systems for Knowledge Management (i.e., concepts and technologies for advancing the availability, connectivity, and interoperability of people, assets, and ideas within an organization) into processes for natural resource science and conservation. As a Science and Technology Policy Fellow, I would like to contribute to better understanding the way federal science is planned, funded, communicated, and leveraged in the broader social, ecological, and geopolitical landscape. I believe publicly funded science, especially science produced or contracted out by federal organizations, should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reproducible (FAIR). I continually strive to ensure my research activities are well-documented, reproducible, publicly available (when possible), and leverage extant (as opposed to collecting new) data and information. For example, my graduate research emphasized the use of participatory science (i.e., citizen science) to advance basic understanding of wildlife populations. I also contributed to the advancement of the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reproducible) principles and Open Science in ecology. I have made my research publically available through numerous, free-to-use scientific softwares, publications in and peer-reviews for open source publications, and invited contributions of my perspectives and experiences to working (e.g., NCEAS Future of Synthesis in Ecology) and focus groups (e.g., NSF 'Missing Millions' focus group).

Complementary to my research skills and motivations, I can also contribute my experience in planning, conducting, and communicating science to diverse audiences in my position as a Science and Technology Policy Fellow. During graduate school, I taught students about population and invasion ecology as well as developed and delivered learning modules and courses for professionals and non-professionals. I also taught statistical programming languages to peers, developed and delivered a module for the Florida Master Naturalist Program, and organized and participated in hands-on outreach activities for local youth. During my PhD, I was invited to co-develop and lead a week-long workshop on statistical programming for Nebraska's state wildlife agency professionals and also worked closely with Dept. of Defense civil servants to identify and serve the science needs of the Eglin Air Force and Fort Riley military bases. As a Young Scholar at the International Institute of Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) in Austria, I further improved my scientific communication skills by working closely with and communicating results to scientists of numerous nationalities who had diverse cultural, educational, and disciplinary backgrounds. My technical and non-technical scientific communication skills are further demonstrated through my publication and presentation record, which includes peer-reviewed scientific journal articles, book chapters, popular science blog posts, governmental reports, and conference, small-group, and outreach presentations. I have three criteria for identifying professional appointments throughout my career: (1) expose underrepresented and underserved individuals to opportunities in ecology and adjacent disciplines; (2) conduct or help shape research activities to improve the state of the environment; and, (3) mentor students and professionals in my field, particularly those with whom I identify (e.g., first generation college students and individuals with disabilities). I wish to apply my research skills and disciplinary interests to real-world, environmental problems while advancing the underlying science. Unlike academia or industry, my career goals and aspirations for professional and personal growth are well-aligned with not-for-profit NGOs (e.g., Audubon Society, The Nature Conservancy) and federal science organizations (e.g., USGS, NASA). Although I am especially interested in working in an organization that affords me the opportunity to advance science, I am open to working in an agency with mandates, like FWS or USDA, where I could continue to advance and apply statistical methods for real-world problems. I believe I could thrive in an agency that has already developed mechanisms for Knowledge Management (e.g., NASA Office of the Chief Knowledge Officer) or at an agency that lacks these formal mechanisms, within which I can contribute relevant disciplinary expertise (e.g., FWS Science Applications, USGS Headquarters).

It is my understanding that the Science and Technology Policy Fellowship experience exposes fellows to career opportunities of which they were previously unaware. As such, I fully expect this opportunity to

accelerate, if not alter, my career trajectory. As a fellow, I will use this opportunity to expand my network beyond colleagues in research and development, not only to broaden my understanding of the role of science in the federal government, and to identify where my skill set and passions may be more effectively leveraged. Although it depends on the host agency and assignment, I look forward to gaining a deeper understanding of the role of science in natural resource decision making at the federal level and, at a minimum, apply this new understanding to improve the Knowledge Management systems for wildlife management and ecological research. Finally, by providing unique insight into the benefits, challenges, and responsibilities of leading in the federal government, I believe this experience will help me more effectively realize change within my future research and professional appointments.

Extracurricular Activities (3500 Character Limit)

STEM OUTREACH

Community Involvement

- Letters to a Pre-scientist (2018-present)
- Skype a Scientist, Virtual (2017-present)
- Secured grant to develop on-site nature trail and wildlife viewing opportunities at the Reichert House in Florida (2014-15)
- Organized hands-on wildlife handling events for students of the Reichert House, Gainesville, FL (2014-15)
- Live bird banding demonstrations and bird watching activities for K-12 students, A Girls' Place, Gainesville, FL (2013-15)
- Science, mathematics, and reading tutor for middle and high school students, Friends of the Micanopy Library, FL (2011-13)
- Learning assistant and tutor for mathematics students, Valencia Community College, Orlando, FL (2008-10)

Blogs

- Connecting to nature and understanding ecosystem services: urban perspective, Envirobotics
- Big data, big problems
- Panarchy in the Anthropocene - Regime shifts, traps and how to deal with them
- Connecting to nature and understanding ecosystem services: the urban perspective
- Leadership resilience and your workplace

Podcasts

- House Sparrow declines in North America, Urban Wildlife Podcast

SERVICE

Peer Review Activity

- Journal articles: Bioinvasions Records (1), Conservation Biology (1), Ecological Informatics (6), Ecological Modelling (4), Journal of Molluscan Studies (2), Landscape and Urban Planning (2), PLOS One (1), Wilson Journal of Ornithology (3)
- Code and software: Journal of Open Source Software (3), ReScience (1)

- Department of Interior: Abstracts (2), Research Articles (2), Software/code (1), Reports (2)

Service at the Department of Interior

- Co-author, FEVS Analysis Team for Core Science Systems Science Analytics and Synthesis (2021)
- Member, Federal Advisory Committee for Avian Knowledge Network (2019-present)
- Member, Communications and Marketing Committee for the North American Breeding Bird Survey 2020 Action Plan (2020-21)

Service at the University of Nebraska-Lincoln

- Conference abstract reviewer, Ecological Society of America (2021)
- Co-founder, Natural Resources Diversity Initiative committee, School of Natural Resources (2017)
- Faculty Advisory Committee, School of Natural Resources (2016-18)
- Student Representative, Faculty search committee for Urban Forestry position, University of Nebraska-Lincoln (2016-17)
- Co-founder, Institutional membership to the Association for Women in Science (2016)
- Digital Team, School of Natural Resources (2016)
- Organizer, Association for Women in Science Mentor Workshop (2016)
- Seminar Coordinator, School of Natural Resources (2016)
- Department Representative, UNL Graduate Student Association (2015 - 16)
- Student Liaison, Urban Ecosystem Ecology Section, Ecological Society of America (2015 - 16)

Service at the University of Florida

- Chair, Student Travel Grant Award Committee, Dept. of Wildlife Ecology and Conservation (2012-13)
 - Contributed feedback on applicants to 3 faculty positions in the department, University of Florida (2012-13)
 - Treasurer, Student Graduate Association, Dept. of Wildlife Ecology and Conservation, (2011-13)
 - Member, Natural Resources Diversity Initiative (2011-13)
 - Member, EcoThinkTank Graduate Student Group (2011-13)
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Applicant Agreement & Signature

Ethics Statement (Please Initial)	JLB
Service in Governance or Policy Committee Positions (Please Initial)	JLB
Federally-Funded Grants, Research Collaborations or Appointments (Please Initial)	JLB
Speaking Engagements & Publishing (Please Initial)	JLB
Honoraria from External Parties (Please Initial)	JLB
Conflict of Interest (Please Initial)	JLB

Certification of Accuracy (Please Initial)

JLB

Statement of Commitment

Yes, I commit to being available for an online selection interview, (if applicable) the Executive Branch placement interviews and the STPF orientation. I also commit to being available to work full-time for the first three months of the fellowship.

Signature

Jessica Leigh Burnett

JESSICA L. BURNETT

Research Ecologist & Mendenhall Postdoctoral Fellow

☎ +1 720-730-0974 ✉ jburnett@usgs.gov

Education

Ph.D. Natural Resource Sciences (Applied Ecology), University of Nebraska-Lincoln	2019
M.Sc. Wildlife Ecology & Conservation, University of Florida	2015
B.Sc. Wildlife Ecology & Conservation University of Florida	2013
A.A. General studies Valencia Community College	2010

Research Experience

Research Ecologist (GS-12), U.S. Geological Survey, Lakewood, Colorado, USA

September 2019 - present

- Developed knowledge graph for improving the provenance of U.S. bird conservation and management.
- Developed framework for evaluating the users and uses of a USGS data program using informatics and social science methods. Made recommendations to program administrations for improving value of agency's data assets to stakeholders.
- Co-led grant application (funded) to Canadian Institute for Ecology and Evolution to fund a year-long working group. Developed software and database for analyzing environmental data for abrupt change and regime shifts.
- Co-led grant application (funded) for Earth Science Information Partnership working group. Developed knowledge graph for assisting with the documentation and development of U.S. State Wildlife Action Plans.
- Authored 2 peer-reviewed research articles, 1 federal agency report, and 3 R packages.

Graduate Research Assistant, Nebraska Cooperative Fish & Wildlife Research Unit, University of Nebraska-Lincoln (UNL), Nebraska

August 2015 - August 2019

- Developed and evaluated statistical methods for detecting abrupt change in ecological and paleoecological communities.
- Worked closely with U.S. military base land managers to meet research needs and communicate results.
- Published 7 peer-reviewed articles, 1 book chapter, 3 reports, and 5 software packages.
- Co-developed and taught week-long scientific programming workshop to state wildlife agency practitioners and university students.
- Co-founder of the university's Chapter of the Association for Women in Science (AWIS). Worked closely with university administration to initiate institutional membership in AWIS. Organized mentoring workshop.

Young Scholar, Applied Systems Analysis Research Group, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), Austria

May 2018 - September 2018

- Developed novel method for detecting regime shifts in paleoecological data (system velocity).
- Conducted research with an international team of applied mathematicians and systems scientists. Presented research in an international forum.
- Organized seminar on Network Analysis in Ecology.
- 1 of 51 scholars from 27 countries of ~400 applicants.

Graduate Teaching Assistant, Department of Wildlife Ecology & Conservation, University of Florida, Florida, USA

August 2013 - August 2015

- Taught population ecology, invasion ecology, and scientific programming to university students.
- Published 2 peer-reviewed scientific articles.
- Led grant application to develop nature trail and receive nature-based educational materials for a local, non-profit organization aimed to reduce recidivism among community youth. Organized after school activities of hands-on wildlife interactions with youth.

Geospatial Analyst Intern, Florida Fish and Wildlife Research Institute, Gainesville, FL

April 2012 - August 2012

- Designed and completed geospatial analysis of raptor and owl nest locations and nesting success.
- Performed ground-truthing of habitat data.

Undergraduate Research Assistant, Avian Ecology and Conservation Lab, University of Florida

January 2011 - April 2012

- Developed and published field method for improved detection of Red-shouldered Hawk (*Buteo lineatus*).
- Managed laboratory's bird banding database.
- After school tutor for low-income middle school students at local library.

Crew Leader and Smithsonian Fellow, Neighborhood Nestwatch Program, Gainesville, Florida

May - July 2012 & April - August 2013

- Trained and led team of 3 bird banding technicians.
- Led community outreach programs for youth in state-sponsored after school and summer programs.
- Recruited and trained participatory scientists.
- Created and distributed outreach materials for program participants.

Publications

1. **Burnett, J.L.**, R. Dale, C.Y. Hou, G. Palomo-Muñoz, K.S. Whitney, S. Aulenbach, R.S. Bristol, D. Valle, and T. Wellman (*accepted*). Ten Simple Rules for Creating a Scientific Web Application. *PLoS Computational Biology*
2. Erickson, R.A., **Burnett, J.L.**, M.T. Wiltermuth, E.A. Bulliner, and L. Hsu (2021). Paths to computational fluency for natural resource educators, researchers, and managers. *Natural Resource Modeling* DOI: [10.1111/nrm.12318](https://doi.org/10.1111/nrm.12318)
3. **Burnett, J.L.** and C.R. Allen. 2020. Continental analysis of invasive Birds: North America in Downs, C.T. and Hart, L.A. (eds) *Invasive Birds: Global Trends and Impacts*. CABI International, Wallingford, UK, pp. 278-294.
4. **Burnett, J.L.**, L.S. Wszola, and G. Palomo-Muñoz. 2019. bbsAssistant: An R package for downloading and handling data and information from the North American Breeding Bird Survey. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 4(44), 1768, DOI: [10.21105/joss.01768](https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.01768)
5. Donovan, V.M., **Burnett, J.L.**, C.H. Bielski, H.E. Birge, R. Bevans, D. Twidwell, and C.R. Allen. 2018. Social-ecological landscape patterns predict woody encroachment from native tree plantings in a temperate grassland *Ecology and Evolution* 8(19): 9624-9632 DOI:[10.1002/ece3.4340](https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.4340)
6. **Burnett, J.L.**, K.L. Pope, A. Wong, C.R. Allen, D.M. Haak, B.J. Stephen, and D.R. Uden. 2018. Thermal tolerance limits of the invasive Chinese mysterysnail *Bellamya chinensis* and implications for management. *American Malacological Bulletin* 36(1): 140-144 DOI:[10.4003/006.036.0106](https://doi.org/10.4003/006.036.0106)

7. Roberts, C.P., D. Twidwell, **Burnett, J.L.**, V.M. Donovan, C. Wonkka, C.H. Bielski, A.S. Garmestani, D.G. Angeler, T. Eason, B.W. Allred, M.O. Jones, D.E. Naugle, S. Sundstrom, C.R. Allen . 2018. Early warnings for state transitions. *Rangeland Ecology and Management* DOI:[10.1016/j.rama.2018.04.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rama.2018.04.012)
8. La Sorte, F.A., C.A. Lepczyk, **Burnett, J.L.**, A. Hurlbert, M. Tingley, and B. Zuckerberg. 2018. Opportunities and challenges for big data ornithology. *The Condor* 120(2): 414-426 DOI:[0.1650/CONDOR-17-206.1](https://doi.org/10.1650/CONDOR-17-206.1)
9. Chuang, W.C., A.S. Garmestani, T. Eason, T.L. Spanbauer, H.B. Fried-Peterson, C. Roberts, S. Sundstrom, **Burnett, J.L.**, D. G. Angeler, B. Chaffin, L. Gunderson, D. Twidwell, C.R. Allen. 2018. Enhancing quantitative approaches for assessing ecological and community resilience. *Journal of Environmental Management* 213: 353-362 DOI:[10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.01.083](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2018.01.083)
10. **Burnett, J.L.**, Roberts, C.P., Allen, C.R., Angeler, D.G., Twidwell, D. 2017. White Paper: Regime Shift Detection Using Fisher Information. Strategic Environmental Research and Development Program (SERDP RC 25-10), Department of Defense.
11. Allen, C.R., Angeler, D.G., Twidwell, D., **Burnett, J.L.**, Roberts, C.P. 2017. Interim Report (RC 25-10): Global Change, Vulnerability, and Resilience: Management Options for an Uncertain Future. Strategic Environmental Research and Development Program (SERDP), Department of Defense.
12. Twidwell D., Bielski, C.H., **Burnett, J.L.**, Donovan, V.M., Wonkka, C.L. 2017. Review of LANDFIRE Biophysical Settings Models (BpS) in the Great Plains. LANDFIRE Project.
13. **Burnett, J.L.**, C.R. Allen, C.P. Roberts, M.Bomberger Brown, and M.P. Moulton. 2017. Eurasian Tree Sparrow (*Passer montanus*) range expansion in North America. *Biological Invasions* 19(1): 5-9 DOI:[10.1007/s10530-016-1273-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10530-016-1273-4)
14. **Burnett, J.L.** and K.E. Sieving. 2016. Songbird distress call as a detection enhancement method and application to Red-shouldered Hawks (*Buteo lineatus*). *Florida Field Naturalist* 44(4):157-168
15. C.R. Allen, H.E. Birge, S.L. Bartlet-Hunt, R.A. Bevans, **Burnett, J.L.**, B.A. Cosens, X. Cai, A.S. Garmestani, I. Linkov, E.A. Scott, M.D. Solomon, and D.R. Uden. 2016. Avoiding decline: Fostering resilience and sustainability in midsize cities. *Sustainability* 8(9):844-868 DOI:[10.3390/su8090844](https://doi.org/10.3390/su8090844)
16. **Burnett, J.L.** and M.P. Moulton. 2015. Recent trends in House Sparrow (*Passer domesticus*) distribution and abundance in Gainesville, Alachua County, Florida. *Florida Field Naturalist* 43(4):167-172

Research Grants

Funded

1. Wee, B., **Burnett, J.L.**, S. Aulenbach, W. Teng, R.A. Modeling data and information needs for avian conservation using Neo4j. Earth Science Information Partners Lab (\$3,388)
2. Pedersen, E., **Burnett, J.L.**, G. Simpson, C. Bahlai. 2020. Creating a unified approach to evaluate regime shift detection methods. Canadian Institution for Ecology and Evolution (CIEE) (\$10,000)
3. **Burnett, J.L.**. 2019-21. Mendenhall Postdoctoral Research, Core Science Systems Science Analytics and Synthesis, U.S. Geological Survey. (\$222,000)
4. **Burnett, J.L.**. 2018 International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) [Young Scholar Summer Program](#). Funding sources: National Academy of Sciences and University of Nebraska-Lincoln. (\$12,500)
5. **Burnett, J.L.** 2013. IFAS Extension Internship for Undergraduate Research, University of Florida. (\$2,200)
6. **Burnett, J.L.** 2013. Ordway-Swisher Biological Station Undergraduate Research Grant, University of Florida. (\$550)

Scientific Software and Source Code

Lifecycle: maturing, stable

1. **Burnett, J.L.**, L.S. Wszola, and G. Palomo-Munoz. 2019. [bbsAssistant](#): An R package for downloading and handling data and information from the North American Breeding Bird Survey: U.S. Geological Survey software release. DOI: [10.5066/P93WoEAW](#).
2. Price, N.B., C. Chizinski, and **Burnett, J.L.**. [radsets](#). An R package for interactive, network-based visualizations of overlapping sets. [Github:natbprice/radsets](#)
3. **Burnett, J.L.**, N.B. Price, and A.J. Tyre. [distanceTravelled](#). An R package for calculating the distance traveled by a multispecies community along a time series.
4. Price, N.B. and **Burnett, J.L.**. [tvdiff](#). An R package for numerical differentiation of noisy, non-smooth data. [Github:natbprice/tvdiff](#)

Lifecycle: experimental

1. **Burnett, J.L.**, K.R. Burgio, A. Fournier [USAvian](#): An interactive map for connecting and visualizing the bird conservation and management networks in the U.S.
2. **Burnett, J.L.**, X. Benito, and K. Braziunas. [abruptdata](#). An R package and information repository for ecological datasets exhibiting abrupt change.

Lifecycle: dormant

1. **Burnett, J.L.**, N.B. Price. [regimeDetectionMeasures](#). An R package for calculating univariate and multivariate regime detection methods using community time series.

Select Honors & Awards

- USGS FY2021 Performance Award (2021)
- Invited focus group participant, NSF Missing Millions (2021)
- USGS FY2020 Performance Award (2020)
- Invited workshop participant, Future of Synthesis in Ecology, NCEAS (2020)
- [Meritorious Graduate Student](#) award, School of Natural Resources, UNL (2018) \$500
- National Academy of Sciences research award (2018) \$5,500
- Invited Participant, [Workshop for Women in Mathematical Biology, NIMBIOS](#) (2018) \$900
- Big Ten Academic Alliance Traveling Scholar (2017)
- Fling Fellow, UNL (2016) \$20,000
- Othmer Fellow (1 university-wide recipient annually), UNL (2016) \$24,000
- Graduate Fellow, Center for Great Plains Studies, UNL (2016)
- Resilience Alliance Young Scholar, The Resilience Alliance (2015-2017)

Conference Symposia and Special Session Organizer

1. Using the integrated modelling framework to bridge science and decision making: advances, applications, and opportunities. Co-organizer with J.A. Royle. Ecological Society of America conference (2020)
2. Bridging the gap between science and decision-making through the rapid prototyping of decision support tools. Co-organizer with D. Valle and L.S. Wszola. Ecological Society of America conference (2020)
3. Opportunities and Challenges in Big Data Ornithology. Co-organizer with F.A. LaSorte and C.A. Lepczyk. North American Ornithological Conference V, Washington, D.C. (2016)

Select Presentations (last 5 years)

Invited

1. Integrating data and information to enhance the digital efficiency of wildlife conservation and management. North American Ornithological Conference (2020)
2. Invited Seminar Speaker, Regime Detection Measures for the Practical Ecologist, Department of Wildlife Ecology & Conservation, University of Florida (2019)
3. Detecting abrupt change in bird community time series using distance traveled. *Association for Women in Math Biology Symposium*, Special session "Current Challenges in Mathematical Biology", Houston, TX (2019)

Contributed

1. **Burnett, J.L.**, N.B. Price, and A.J. Tyre. A novel method for tracking ecosystem trajectory and abrupt change in space-time: distance traveled. *International Association for Landscape Ecology*, Oral presentation. Fort Collins, CO (2019)
2. **Burnett, J.L.**, R. Crystal-Ornelas, D. Fogarty, K. Hogan, C.R. Allen, M. Bomberger Brown, D. Twidwell, and C.A. Lepczyk. Impacts of non-native birds on native wildlife in urban ecosystems: where is the evidence? *Natural Areas Conference*, Oral presentation. Indiana (2018)
3. **Burnett, J.L.**. Advances in ecological regime shift detection, *International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis*, Oral presentation. Laxenburg, Austria (2018)
4. **Burnett, J.L.**, N.B. Price, A.J. Tyre, T.J. Hefley, C.R. Allen, T. A. Eason, D.G. Angeler, and D. Twidwell. Community velocity as a regime shift detection method. *Great Plains Grassland Summit*, Poster presentation. Denver, Colorado (2018)
5. **Burnett, J.L.**, L. Wszola, N. Mirochnitchenko, E. Stuber, M. Bomberger Brown, C.R. Allen, D. Twidwell, and J.P. Carroll (presenter). Gray partridge distribution in North America: Changing landscapes and environment for an introduced species. *Perdix XIV and IUGB*, Oral presentation by JPC, Montpellier, France (2017)
6. **Burnett, J.L.**, N.B. Price, A.J. Tyre, T.J. Hefley, C.R. Allen, T. A. Eason, D.G. Angeler, and D. Twidwell. System trajectory and Fisher information as early-warning indicators of ecological regime shifts. *Resilience 2017: Resilience Frontiers for Global Sustainability*, Poster presentation. Stockholm, Sweden (2017)

Select Certifications, Workshops, and Professional Development Training

- Leadership and Management Skills for Non-managers, Management Concepts 2021
- USGS 12-month Mentoring Program (mentee) 2020-21
- USGS Principled Centered Leadership (USGS-PCL) 2020
- Gauging Your Leadership Performance 2020
- Defining Alternative Solutions to a Problem 2020
- Aligning Goals and Priorities to Manage Time 2020
- Structured Decision Making Workshop (observer) 2020
- High Performance Computing in R and Python 2020
- Software Carpentries 2015
- Basic Wildland Firefighting (SF-1390, SF-190) 2013